

Challenges of Child Immunisation in Rural India : A Sociological Study

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Abstract

India has one of the lowest immunisation rates worldwide despite a longstanding universal immunisation programme (UIP) that provides free childhood vaccines. There are probably cultural and / or religious factors that act as an impediment of vaccination. The government of India is rapidly building public health infrastructure and manpower to improve vaccination rates, but other factors such as cultural, socio- economic and religious are not being addressed. In India there are many childhood deaths from vaccines – preventable illness in India at high levels, the reason is – lack of education and awareness for parents on the benefits of vaccination. This study highlights the need to develop a much better understanding of the cultural factors that influence childhood vaccination in India.

Keywords

Cultural Belief, Vaccination, Health Promotion, Health Communication, Vaccine.

Introduction

Child immunisation involves administering vaccines to children to develop immunity against specific diseases. Vaccines stimulate the body's immune system to recognize and combat harmful pathogens. Immunisation is in preventing outbreaks of diseases such as measles, polio and hepatitis. By protecting children through vaccination, communities can reduce the overall prevalence of certain diseases. It is essential to ensure that all children have may be limited.

Objective of study

1. This paper explores the importance of Child Immunisation and identifies challenges and potential solutions for rural regions.
2. To protect rural children from diseases that can cause serious harm or death and to prove help them grow up healthy.
3. To spread awareness about the importance of child immunisation among the rural India.

Review of Literature

The Lancet Global Health, Mira Johri and colleagues have estimated the prevalence of zero-dose children in India using data from National Family Health Survey between 1992 and 2016. TheIR analysis indicates that the proportions of zero-dose children in India has declined from 33.4% in 1992 to 10.1% in 2016. TheY estimated 2 .88 Million zero-dose children in 2015-16, with more than 80% living in eightIndian states.

Desai S,Alva S analyse analyse the casual relation between child health and female education .The study uses child mortality, immunisation status ect.and find out that mothers primary as well as secondary education is so statistically significant for infant mortality, an indicator of child's health.

In the Indian context, study of immunisation status of children and female education in M.P. in the context of Universal Immunisation Program (UIP). The multivariate analysis shows an increasing full vaccination with an increasing level of female education. lack of information is the main obstacle of non-immunisation

Nilanjan Patra, book on India's Universal Immunisation Programme using National Family Health Survey tries to find out the factors that explain the under utilisation of immunisation services in India. It also presents the socio-economic predictor variables on the likelihood of a child receiving immunisation for six vaccine – preventable diseases.

De and Bhattacharya examined the factors affecting childhood vaccination in Indian states (Madhya Pradesh ,Bihar, Uttar Pradesh and Rajasthan) and reported lower vaccination coverage among Muslim children compare to other religious group children in all states in India except Madhya Pradesh. In an another study by Kumar et .al. greater overall inequity in vaccination coverage was observed in Maharashtra to Bihar, an economically much poorer states.

Main Text

The importance of child immunisation cannot be overstated, particularly for children in rural India. Globally, in 2023, 4.5 million infants did not receive an initial dose of the DTP (Diphtheria-Tetanus-Pertussis) that but uses, vaccine highlighting a lack of access to innovation and other health services. An additional 6.5 million children or only partially vaccinated source :(who.int.2024)

Even raised children were less likely to suffer illnesses. Furthermore, widespread immunisation helped promote educational opportunities and healthy children can attend school regularly

Immunisation is one of the most cost-effective public health interventions and largely responsible for reduction of mortality and morbidity rates caused by vaccine preventable diseases. The error education of smallpox globally and the elimination of polio, neonatal tetanus from India are clear reminders of the power of vaccination in dealing with the scourge of communicable diseases.

UIP becomes a part of child survival in 1992. Since 1997, immunisation activities have been an important component of the child health programme and is one of the key area under the national health Mission (N.H.M) since 2005. Under the UIP, Government of India is providing vaccination to prevent 11 vaccine preventable diseases, namely diphtheria, pertussis, tetanus, meningitis and pneumonia, tuberculosis, polio, hepatitis B and measles, rubella and rotavirus diarrhoea.

Despite significant spending on childhood immunisation India have not achieved universal coverage of routine childhood vaccine. Understanding the obstacles to vaccination at the local level is crucial for improving the child mortality and health outcomes in India and other LMICs

Mission Indradhanush (MI) was launched by the Ministry of health and family welfare (MoHFW) on 25th December 2014. The primary objective of Mission Indradhanush is to provide comprehensive immunisation coverage to all children under the age of 2 years. The programme is an integral part of the broader health mission programmes that aim to improve health outcomes and prevent the spread of infectious diseases. By focusing on immunisation, am I seeks to protect vulnerable populations from severe illnesses that can have devastating effects on health and well-being.

Despite its success, Mission Indradhanush faces several challenges

Geographic Barriers

Remote and hard to reach areas can make it difficult to administer vaccine. Mobile vaccination units and outreach programs help address these challenges.

Awareness and Education:

Ensuring that communities are aware of the importance of vaccination and addressing any misconceptions is crucial for increasing vaccine uptake

Supply Chain Management

Efficient management of vaccine supply and distribution is essential to prevent shortages and ensure timely availability.

Mission Indradhanush has made significant strides in improving immunisation coverage in India. Key achievement includes:

1. The programme has successfully increased the number of children receiving vaccinations, contributing to reduce incidence of vaccine – preventable diseases.
2. By protecting individuals from severe illnesses, Mission Indradhanush has helped reduce morbidity and mortality rates associated with the targeted diseases.
3. The programme has raised awareness about the importance of vaccination and encouraged more people to participate in immunisation efforts

Universal Immunisation Programme

The Immunisation Programme is one of the key interventions for the protection of children from life-threatening conditions, which are preventable. It is one of the largest immunisation programmes in the world and a major public health intervention in the country.

The Immunisation Programme in India was introduced in 1978 as the Expanded Programme of Immunisation (EPI).

The Program gained momentum in 1985 and was expanded as Universal even Immunisation Programme (UIP) to be implemented in a phased manner to cover all districts in the country.

UIP become a part of the Child Survival and State Motherhood Programme in 1992. Since,1997, immunisation activities have been an important component of the national reproductive and child health programme and are currently one of the key areas under the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) since 2005.

Under the Universal Immunisation Programme the Government of India is providing vaccination to prevent eleven vaccine preventable diseases i.e., Diphtheria, Pertussis, Tetanus, Polio, Measles, Rubella, severe form of Childhood Tuberculosis, Hepatitis- B, Haemophilus influenza type B (HIB) Pneumococcal and Diarrhoeas due to Rotavirus.

Child immunisation in rural India is challenging due to a few factors. Understanding these challenges is crucial for developing effective strategies to improve vaccination coverage and ensure that every time you see protection against preventable diseases.

Access to health care facilities

Access to health care facilities poses a significant challenge for child immunisation in rural areas of India. Many villages lack nearby health centres or clinics, making it difficult for families to access immunisation services.

Transportation barriers such as poor road conditions and limited public transport further complicate access. Many children may not be able to get crucial vaccinations without convenient options, putting their health at risk.

Lack of Awareness and Misinformation

Parents can hesitate about vaccinations considering the misinformation surrounding child immunisation. Many families in rural areas may not fully understand the importance of vaccinations or may have misconceptions about vaccine safety.

This lack of knowledge can result in delays or refusal to immunize children. Community education initiatives are essential to eradicate these myths and promote the benefits of vaccination.

Social economic barriers

Social economic barriers significantly impact child immunisation rates in rural areas. Families with low income may prioritise immediate needs such as food and shelter over healthcare.

Additionally, some families may lack the resources to travel to health centres for immunisation. Addressing the social - economic challenges is crucial to ensuring equitable access to vaccinations for all children.

Supply chain issues and vaccine storage

Supply chain issues and vaccine storage presents significant challenges for child immunisation in rural areas. Vaccines require specific storage conditions to remain effective and rural health facilities may lack adequate refrigeration. Interruptions in the supply chain can lead to vaccine shortages, further delaying immunisation efforts. Improving logistics and infrastructure ensures vaccines are available and properly stored.

Barriers for the programme are:

There are many financial and non-financial barriers which are responsible for delay or prevent people in the rural areas from seeking healthcare for mothers and their children. Such barriers include - financial barriers, geographical access or distance, language, social - cultural, ethnicity related barriers, lack of knowledge and awareness, and inequalities in quality of care which can together lead to low demand for and use of services, particularly by the poor.

Availability of critical components required to deliver the health services such as infrastructure human resources and financial resources to run the programme. Health facilities should be established as per the population norms and they should be well equipped with trained healthcare providers and equipment as per IPHS standards.

Barriers to utilisation describes the use of multi - contact services example first antenatal contact or BCG immunisation .Cost of care, distance from health facilities and poor quality of care (including factors such absence of staff at health facilities and long waiting times), poor upkeep of facilities non-functional equipment are the major reasons why people do not seek care from public health facilities.

Lack of time, unawareness, long waiting hours, fear of adverse event, concern related to loss of daily income are also some of the major challenges or reasons for not getting their children vaccinated. Poor /rude behaviour of the staff was an important factor that led to either delayed or missed immunisation.

New vaccines, have been introduced and expanded nationwide even then, challenges remain. In 2022, 14.330,000 infants did not receive the first DPT vaccine globally, pointing to a lack of access to immunisation and other health services. (UNICEF)

{60% Unvaccinated kids live in 10 countries}

India ranks second with 16lakh 'Zero-dose' children after Nigeria's 21lakh

Percentage of 'Zero-dose' in 2023

Nigeria-----15%

India-----11%

DRC-----	6%
Ethiopia-----	6%
Indonesia-----	5%
Sudan-----	5%
Yemen-----	4%
Afghanistan-----	3%
Angola-----	3%
Pakistan-----	3%

Zero-dose children are those who did not receive a first dose -Diphtheria -Tetanus – Pertussis - (including factors such as DPT)

Source - WHO/UNICEF

In 2022, India ranked third among the top 20 countries with the highest number of Zero-dose, children trailing behind Nigeria and Ethiopia. India saw a 0.45 million rise in Zero-dose children from 2022 to 2023.

In India 1.6 million children did not receive a single dose of the DTP vaccine or the measles containing vaccine MCV in 2023. According to the WHO–UNICEF report, ‘over the last five years measles outbreak hit 103 countries home to roughly three- quarters of the world’s infants. Low vaccine coverage (80% or less) was a major factor in contrast 91 countries with strong measles vaccine coverage did not experience outbreaks.

However, globally, the number of children who received three doses of the vaccine against the DTP in 2023 stalled at 84% (108 million).

Additionally, the third dose of the polio vaccine had a coverage rate of 57% in 2000, which increased slightly to 91% by 2003 in India.

According to Alka Gupta, communications specialist at UNICEF India, challenges for full immunisation coverage include - geographic disparities, access to services in urban-poor, rural and remote areas, migration and socio-economic barriers. She told India today that other common reasons for missing vaccine doses include awareness information gaps, the Adverse Effect Following Immunisation (AEFI) apprehensions and children not being at home or parents refusing vaccination.

Per Gupta, ‘India is one of the countries that saw an increase in the perception of the importance of vaccines for children. Community-based outreach to women in India has proven effective in improving vaccine confidence and immunisation rates. Studies have shown that incorporating health education into women’s self-help group meetings using stories, songs and pictures puzzle can boost age - appropriate immunisation by nine percent.

Solutions to Improve Child Immunisation in Rural Areas

Ensuring children in rural areas receive essential immunisations requires targeted strategies and collaborative efforts. Various approaches including government policies, mobile clinics, community education and public- private partnerships, are vital to achieving widespread vaccination coverage.

Government Policies and Immunisation Programme

Government policies and immunisation programme play a crucial role in enhancing child immunisation rates in rural India. National initiatives aim to provide vaccines to all children, often offering free vaccinations through public health programmes. These policies help ensure that every child receive the necessary immunisation.

Mobile Clinics and Outreach Programmes

Mobile clinics and outreach programmes can effectively improve child immunisation in rural areas. These initiatives bring healthcare services directly to communities, making it easier for families to assess vaccinations.

This programme can reach un-deserved populations through regular humanisation drives in villages.

Community Education and Awareness Campaigns

Community education and awareness campaigns are essential for promoting the importance of child immunisation.

By informing families is about the benefits and safety of vaccines, these campaigns can help to clear up misinformation and encourage parents to vaccinate their children. Child

health NGOs like CRY India play a key role in promoting immunisation by working with local communities to raise awareness, promote health education and bridge gaps in healthcare accessibility.

Government Initiatives and Programmes

The Indian government has undertaken several initiatives to improve child immunisation rates. The National Immunity Programme aims to provide comprehensive vaccination coverage for children across the country. A child is considered fully immunised only when they receive all the scheduled vaccine and other National Immunisation Programme within their first year of birth (source: nhm.gov.in.2024).

Conclusion

Immunisation coverage have improved nationally and in most states of India. Government programmes like Mission Indradhanush will help improve coverage among the communities where it is hard to reach in India, which will help in reducing further inequality related to immunisation .Those who are still not fully immunised represent those with the risk of infectious diseases independent of vaccination status. Our studies suggest that targeted interventions at the state as well as district level will be needed to increase immunisation coverage, to prevent transmission of vaccine – preventable diseases in India. In addition this study indicates that some social determinants of health continue to be associated with immunisation inequality in India.

An inclusive education, health and family welfare approach that improve female schooling, health knowledge and positive attitude towards modern health care among mothers and female empowerment are beneficial for complete vaccination of children in India towards improving child health and reducing child mortality in India.

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